

Pride Vs. Humility : Humbly Proudful or Proudly Humble

Francisco Sionil Jose's novel, *My Brother, My Executioner*, deals with a guerrilla battle where conflicting sides revolve around two siblings. The story shows that the intensity of our beliefs may cause us to do things to pursue what we think is right, but unconsciously, we are only trying to insist on something because of our pride. This pride is always trying to be in the way, especially when people around us think that it is already hopeless already, we still persist (in a negative way) because of our pride. This is very evident in the society, more specifically, in the context of family. The story also deals with resistance to change. Subjectively speaking, conservatism is quite an issue in this modern world. This pertains to the conventional ways people choose to do. It might be true that there are still people who are hesitant to change and adapt with the modern lifestyle. Whereas, there are also people with high tolerance. In this regard, it is necessary to find the balance where people can choose what to do and what not to do.

Let us be open minded with this one. Only a few siblings have healthy relationships with one another. This may be influenced by competition, favoritism by the parents, and comparing issues from people inside and outside the family. The usual outcome when the pride insists is that the one who is faced with negative outcomes blames other people for his or her failure despite all the efforts he or she has exerted. Because of this, we must do our best to educate people not to compare themselves with others. It is common knowledge to know about individuals having their own uniqueness. Senseless and comparison with people will only bring hatred to one another. In fact, many baseless and useless quarrels in the family that happen point out this question "Why can't I be as good as brother/sister?" The idea of comparing oneself to other people, especially to one's siblings will never do good in the family. Most typical escalated examples to this scenario include fighting over rights for lands and properties. Their mindset (also driven by their pride) is that they are focused on becoming greater than anyone in their family. They seek recognition, satisfaction, and special treatment over trivial matters. Supposedly, siblings are people that should help one another. But that is not the only issue, there are more troubling matters like blaming others for their failures. Suppose that Charles is the eldest in the family. He asked his younger brother to bring him water at his track and field screening. Bryan, the younger brother, agreed to bring him water. But on the track, Charles failed to catch the water bottle Bryan is holding. Because of Charles' stubbornness and pride, he chose to continue the race without drinking water. With less energy, he lost the chance to be part of the team and blamed Bryan all over until they were settled by their parents at home. Truly, this deed is an act

of immaturity and pride. They could have just talked about things over. They do not really need to fight, especially Charles, he should have not blamed Bryan. After all, his efforts neglecting the help of Bryan resulted in failure. In the field of teaching, pre-service teachers must devote time and effort in developing themselves to learn the nature of these kinds of things. Only by proper training and instruction, we be able to handle such scenarios in the near future. Another issue that is caused by pride is the faulty resistance in changes brought by modernity. More specifically the issue of conservatism. It is characterized by people who have no sense of acceptance with the conventional way of living such as the use of technology. They are people who will insist with the reasoning, "I was born in this way, I should die in this way." Well, these cases are rarely found, but are horribly annoying. The very common examples are the actions or behavior of people who live in informal settlements (locally known as living in the squatters areas). Most of them chose to fight back against persons in authority because of their intolerance to changes. Another thing is the orientation of letting the wife stay at home and letting the husband do the work in a family. This kind of orientation is not actually a problem. However, the problem arises when people insist that they should strictly comply with this orientation without complaints. Now what happens to equality? What happens to the freedom of choosing what is best for us, if we adhere to this stereotypical set-up? These kinds of cases are truly debatable and without doubt, many are still fighting with their parents, neighbors, relatives, and peers just to get rid of this conservative lifestyle. Hypothetically, individuals who choose to agree with conservatism should be blamed when people would end up committing suicides because of this unfair and unconventional practices. But no, they are just simply trying to convince us to choose to live our lives in conservative manner. Where in fact, one has the freedom to choose and to do what he or she knows will never harm others.

To think of it rationally, let us just treat their conservative ideas as options where we can choose to. We have control over our lives and so we must live our lives with honor and humility. This juxtaposition means that we must do what is best for us. We can back down anytime when we feel aggravated and undignified. More importantly, we must acknowledge our limitations for us to mature. There is no harm in admitting one's weaknesses. We should be proud in admitting them. It is the best way to avoid any harm like what happened to the story in the novel. We should talk things over for it not to cause any more troubles in the future.